

Mart Kalm

Modern city as tool for russification: Estonian experience

Abstract

Ideology

The idea of Modern City to provide population with decent accommodation has been democratic and egalitarian and therefore high-minded. Although these goals have been achieved it doesn't mean the pleasant neighbourhood is created. The architectural rigour and bleakness of environment in planned cities has been widely discussed, but in special cases this negative impact is doubled by state policy of accommodation. History: Starting from Hrushtshov thaw in mid-1950s-modernist cities consisting of only prefabricated Housing were largely built in all Eastern-bloc countries. This step was welcomed in Estonia, a country occupied and heavily bombed by the USSR during the WWII and still suffering under serious shortage of housing. The modern cities were rather imperfect because of the lack of infrastructure and low construction quality. Economic mechanism: In 1960-70s lots of industries were found in Estonia by Soviet officials. As there was not enough labour the workers were imported from the rest of the USSR. There didn't exist free housing market in the USSR and the flats had to be provided by employers. These new industries attracted immigrants thanks to the new flats they offered. National political result: Russian-speaking immigrants inhabited new modern cities and the local Estonians had to remain in old pre-Soviet time housing with rather modest conveniences. Estonians felt Soviet State considers them as second-rate people and Russian-speaking immigrants as privileged. Protection and conservation: Although architectural historians see in Soviet period modern cit-

ies some architectural and urban values the public opinion denies these. For ordinary people the 1960-80s housing estates symbolise russification period and they are against using public money for the revitalisation of these areas. These modern cities are in the condition of decay and ghettos are quickly forming. Conclusion: Twenty years ago Estonians dreamed about possibility to live in new modern city but nowadays they prefer to revitalise old pre-Soviet time housing or to build new estates. Thank to the national-political connotations the idea of modern city was double discredited in Estonia.

KEYWORDS

Housing, russification, colonisation, immigration, culture conflicts

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